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LG / LID: Kunama / 147

Sources: Lionel M. Bender (1996): Kunama;

Languages of the world / Materials 59;
Lincom Europa München – Newcastle;

- ` = low tone
- ´ = high tone
- + = morpheme boundary
- ' = stress on following syllable

1. Phonology

- the main problem is the still incompletely analyzed suprasegmental system, especially tonology
- /r/ is the only consonant which cannot occur word-initially
- long vowels do not occur word finally unless one interprets final “downdrift” falling tones as occurring on VV
- clusters:
 - o /mb/, /nd/, /ŋk/ different analysis as segments or as sequences
 - o never occur word-initially
 - o gW, kW dialectal variants
 - o ŋg, ŋk
 - o other possible clusters are vanishingly rare
 - o consonant + /r/; ex.: àfrìngà ‘pepper’(loan?), bit(i)ri'ta ‘candle’
 - o initials nk-, nn- occur in variation with ink- (phonetically : nk, ng > ŋk, ŋg); ex.: (i)nkál'é
 - o lexical or grammatical germination across syllable boundary is significant though sometimes optional
 - o there are examples for all but /h/, /r/, /ʃ/;
ex.: dabbu ‘since’, gùf 'fàda ‘strut’, na + ggoša + ke ‘I needed’
 - o other non-identical CC clusters across syllable boundaries are quite restricted
 - o obstruents do not occur as C¹ except for /b/ in the ideophone tabtab [~taptap] ~tautau ‘patter of rain’ and /t/ in the reduplicated fat 'fata ‘snake var.: black mamba?)
 - o C¹ position is filled mainly by the resonants /m, n, ŋ, l, r/ and fricatives /f, s, š/
 - o C² position is filled by all consonants except resonants and glides /l, r, h, w, ŋ, ʃ/
 - o Nasals /m/, /n/ occur rarely
- Phonological processes:
 - o Some are dialectal
 - o s + k > s + s , ex.: kos + se ‘he is here, there’
 - o r + m > mm ;ex.: gamma ‘sheep’
 - o sometimes the vowel /i/ palatalizes a following or preceding /s/ ;
ex.: i-ša + ke ‘he became’ (na + sa + ke ‘I became’),
na + kos + ina ~ na + koš + ina ‘I will be here / there’

- the glide /y/ tends to “wander”: eg. faaša ~ fayša ‘beautiful’ (assumption: y<š), naa + niy +te + ke ~ nay + niy + te + ke ‘I found tem, ye’ (might be reanalyzed as a vowel –i-)
 - intrusive (anaptyctic) nasals occur homorganic to immediately following consonant; ex.: maida(m) + be ‘good-is it’, ita(n) + dea ‘ house-it is’
 - vowel harmony is found at least with /i/ and /u/: eg. i + fur + ke > u + fur + ke ‘he saves , rescues him’, i + tuu + ke > u + tuu + ke ‘he put it in , made tea’
 - in fact many u-initial verbs have –u- in the next syllable , exceptions are ùmmà'dà ‘collect’, 'ūa ‘steal’, and verbs with uu-, ex.: ùu'dá ‘say’
 - vowels:
 - reduction in non-prominent position occur, especially a > ə
 - frequent diphthongs: ai, au, oi
 - vowel sequences occurring across syllable boundaries are rare
 - simplification of syllable structure by elimination of postvocalic /w/, /y/
 - stress:
 - significant grammatically, eg. imperative sg. Vs. pl.
 - not clear wether it operates lexically
 - correlated with high tone
 - different analyses:
 - a) usually on the penultimate syllable, but this is not invariable
 - b) words may have final, penult, antepenult stress
 - it is reported that Kunamas themselves often disagree on placement of stress
 - the author has also two degees of stress recorded: "gaabe'da ‘embrace, hug’, "tuku'na ‘peak’ and some with two equal stresses: eg. 'bàd'dà ‘above, up’
 - tone:
 - two level tones and a falling tone
 - the author analyses the falling tone as a high-low sequence on VV or an end-of –word downdrift on final V: eg. bì' à > bià ‘water’
 - also noted some falling tones on possibly short non-final vowels, but in these the tone may spread over an initial nasal or glide: eg. 'nnà ‘this’
 - low tone unmarked
 - Banti (an often cited author, but unpublished)
 - states that tone is syllabic, not moraic (no examples)
- all three suprasegmentals (tone, length, stress) are independent
- syllable and morpheme types:
 - open syllables in final position are the rule
 - open syllables are frequent: V, CV(V)
 - main exceptions are grammatical morphemes and echoic words
 - closed syllables are also frequent, but do not occur finally except in the agent subject suffix –(d)em
 - Banti: nouns from one to four syllables of various tonal combinations
 - Template: CV(V)(C) if V is a diphthong no second vowel is allowed
 - The only word of shape V is ‘e’ ‘yes’ and the only VV is the noun bisyllable ‘e'a’ ‘dream’
 - All other monosyllables are of shape Ca, eg. ma ‘tooth’

- VV may be tautosyllabic long vowels or sequences
- There is an exceptional CCV item: 'nna 'this'
- Nouns are generally of shape C + a or (C)VC + a, where V may be long or short, exception: e'a 'dream' and names, especially borrowed names may have final vowels other than -a
- Bisyllabic, trisyllabic and longer nouns are also found as well as those of shape CVCC + a

2. Morphology and syntax

- Agglutinative morphology
- Word order is not rigid
- compound nouns:
 - manner is indicated by compounds, ex.: sá'ná-tàbi'là 'working-road'
 - construct state; ex.: manna aura 'a chief's speech'
- verbal structure:
 - some verbs of the suffixing conjugation incorporate nouns or borrowed elements, ex.: hi'ha + s + ke 'he (donkey) brayed'
 - in verbal conjugation the suprasegmentals should be regarded as very tentative, stress is elusive, in some cases it seems necessary to record two primary stresses in the same word (not mentioned in which cases)
 - causatives are formed by use of the verb 'do, make' i + míni, ex.: 'ded + oa i + yo + na + si k+ i + min + ke 'boy-the that-he-come he-made'
 - examples of causative forms which may be interpreted as causatives, e.g. lalab- 'dry s.t.' < lab 'be dry', susu 'mediate peace' < su 'give up enmity'
 - passive-reflexive is a syntactic construction of aux +kos+ 'be present' and main verb
 - for passive / reciprocal some use compounding with iša + ke 'became'
 - there is a productive mechanism by which two or more verbs with the same subject occur in sequence with only the final verb having TAM marking while person / number marking occurs on each verb
 - non-final verbs of the first conjugation drop final vowels of person markers
 - converbs:
 - sentences often contain a string of converbs (usually neutral as to tense) describing various serial or simultaneous actions followed by a final verb which is fully marked for person, number, TAM
 - ex.: converbs +ki and +no with while, when:
u'nu ø+i+no+kos+ki ø+i+bal+ke
he 3sg+drink+aux+cnv 3sg+die+Ao
'While he was drinking, he died.' or 'As a result of habitual drinking he died.'
 - differentiation of aux, verb compounds, serial verbs is problematical:
 - compound verbs are V+V constructions which act like a single verb (take person, number, TAM affixes like single verbs)
 - converbs are not serials: they are subordinate verbs marked for TAM
 - aux are also not serials if they have their own TAM marking, but in Kunama aux are sub-class of serial verbs
 - serials are verbs used in sequence with a lexical meaning which is a

composite of the lexical meanings of the component verbs: if the meaning carried by a serial verb contributes to the TAM properties of the main verb, it can be considered an aux

- compound tenses are often formed by serialization: past / present continuous: ime o+latta gon+ke ‘they were writing’ (lit.: ‘they they-write they-stay’), recent past: unu i+latta uta+ke ‘he wrote (just now) (lit.: ‘he he-write he-spent some time’), distant past: ime o+latta (k)o+(y)šii+ke ‘they wrote some time ago’ (lit.: ‘they they-write they-gave birth’)
- postpositions:
 - nominal relationships which can be broadly included under the category of case are realized in Kunama by the use of postpositions
 - postposition si marks direct and indirect object, can also carry the meaning of cause and purpose
 - the –i of si is elided before vowels, ex.: garma umma + s(i) inti + ke ‘He saw a black sheep.’
 - Stipulation that all postpositions are self-standing words with their own accents – not enclitics- and should be separated from nouns (perhaps some are further along becoming case-markers than others)
 - May be compounded, especially with the general locative + la, ex.: bà'dà + la ‘behind, in back of’ - dàlà'mà à'yà + 'bàd'dà + la ‘cloud mountain + above + on’ (= cloud is over mountain)
- Preposition: corresponding to English ‘than’, used to form comparative and superlatives, ex.: ài'là 'ta + kin àn'dà ‘cow dog-from big’
- Independent pronouns (as opposite to affixes): suprasegmentals vary from dialect to dialect, utilizing all three (stress, length, tone)
- Possessive suffixes: may have missed suprasegmentals
- Verb conjugation:
 - Subject prefix 3.sg i + is elided with the indirect object preceding it
 - In 3rd person the presence of i palatalizes following s to š
- Interrogative pronoun: vowel change occur , ex.: ái itano? > ái itino and that the last may be reduced to ai ití? ‘which (= ái) house?’